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Abstract:

The goal of Task 3.4 of Work Package 3 is the development of a versatile online monitoring tool for EUDAQ2, which can be used by any test beam user with any detector setup. This drive towards common software tools aims to prevent multiplication of work by people implementing their own software and to provide a platform which can generally be supported and maintained centrally. This document summarises the concept, final developments, and recent tests and use cases of this monitoring tool.

AIDAinnova Consortium, 2024

For more information on AIDAinnova, its partners and contributors please see <http://aidainnova.web.cern.ch/>

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Executive summary

This deliverable report describes the deployment of the monitoring software developed for the data acquisition control system EUDAQ2. It concludes the work that has been done and presented as part of Milestone 10. Section 1 describes the motivation for this deliverable. In Section 2, the software used that forms the base of the CorryMonitor project is described. Sections 3 and 4 explain the functionality and the use of the CorryMonitor. Section 5 showcases the testing the CorryMonitor underwent with real test beam data. In Section 6 a new feature going beyond the scope of the deliverable is explained in detail. The opportunities to promote this project at various conferences are listed in Section 7.

1. INTRODUCTION

Sharing resources and infrastructure is a key aspect in AIDAinnova, especially in WP3, where this is focused on test beam environments, which are a crucial part of any detector development and as such are beneficial to the work of all other WPs.

This common effort is being exerted in both hardware and software infrastructure. This particular task deals with the development of an online monitoring tool for test beam users. Needless to say, having access to a monitoring system to control data taking is of utmost importance during a test beam campaign since it allows users to quickly adapt their data taking to unforeseen circumstances.

The EUDAQ2 package has been developed in the scope of providing a common test beam data acquisition control system and therefore the centrepiece of new software developments within the AIDAinnova project.

A versatile online monitoring therefore has to fulfil these requirements:

- Complete integration into EUDAQ2
- Flexible DUT integration
- User convenience and thorough documentation

2. PROJECT BACKGROUND

2.1. EUDAQ2

EUDAQ2 is data acquisition (DAQ) control system that provides data handling, data storage, log collection, and centralised command distribution [1]. Its architecture follows a modular design approach, where each module connects to the RunControl to receive commands to initialise, configure, start, stop, reset and terminate the module. Figure 1 shows a diagram of the EUDAQ2 architecture. Some of the core components are explained below.

Figure 1 Architecture of the EUDAQ2 framework [1]

Firstly, the Producer that connects EUDAQ2 with the user DAQ systems and generates data. It is typically the user’s responsibility to implement a Producer for their device before coming to the test beam.

Secondly, the DataCollector (DC) retrieves and merges data sent over a network protocol by the Producers and writes it to file. The DataCollector is also responsible for writing the data to file, utilising a converter provided by the user, in which the data from the producer is mapped to so-called ‘planes’ and ‘pixels’.

Lastly a Monitor to ensure the data quality, fed by a single DC. It comes with a few potential issues: The DC can only send a certain fixed fraction of events to the Monitor. This causes back-pressure on the collector if the monitoring cannot keep up with plotting. Additionally, data from multiple collectors cannot be merged and in the currently used ROOT-based StdEventManager, no flexible event building is possible. Figure 2 shows a screenshot of the StdEventManager displaying the hitmaps for the 38 layers of the CALICE AHCAL prototype, which could only be achieved after tweaking the Monitor. Furthermore, the Monitor does contain any information about the setup geometry. This in turn, does not allow for advanced reconstruction of the test beam data during data taking, for instance track reconstruction. Through association of hits on the DUT with the track, users could gain first estimates for their device’s efficiency.

Figure 2 ROOT-based monitor displaying hitmaps of 38 AHCAL layers [1]

Instead of reworking the ROOT-based monitor to include all the desired functionality, the commonly used software *corrvreckan*, created for reconstruction and analysis of test beam data, is used to take care of monitoring for EUDAQ2 as it provides all required functionality.

2.2. CORRYVRECKAN

Corrvreckan is a reconstruction and analysis software for test beam data [2]. It is developed and maintained by members of the pixel detector community and has found a wide user base there.

Its modular design allows for a large variety of use-cases. For instance, there are modules responsible for event loading, clustering, tracking, or offline alignment. Each of these modules produces their own plots which can be viewed during the reconstruction process using the graphical user interface the software provides. These reconstructions can be very useful during a test beam to gain a first estimate on the device-under-test (DUT) performance.

The software is actively being maintained, with many contributions from the community. It also enjoys the benefit of having extensive documentation making it extremely user friendly.

2.2.1. Compatibility with EUDAQ2

Corrvreckan can read `eudaq::StdEvents` via a dedicated module, `EventLoaderEUDAQ2`. This module internally calls an `eudaq::NativeFileReader` to read in events and convert them to corrvreckan events ready for further analysis. This module requires only an EUDAQ2 installation and the `eudaq::RawEvent2StdEventConverter` for the data that is to be read. Since this converter needs to be prepared by the user anyway in order to write the data to file, this compatibility comes for free with no further work required from neither the developing team nor the user.

2.2.2. Information about setup geometry

```
[my_ex0_plane_0]
number_of_pixels = 16, 16
orientation = 0deg, 0deg, 0deg
orientation_mode = "xyz"
pixel_pitch = 55um, 55um
position = 0um, 0um, 0um
role = "dut", "reference"
time_resolution = -1ns
type = "ex0raw"
```

Figure 3 Example for a corrvreckan geometry file

Via a geometry file, which needs to be written by the user, corrvreckan has information about the geometry of the test beam setup. The structure of the file is shown in Figure 3 for the random data produced by the example Producer `eudaq::Ex0Producer`. In this example, random data with raw values between 0 and 255 is created in one plane in a 16×16 pixel grid. In the geometry file one section, distinguished by the header in the square brackets, corresponds to one plane. The parameters from the geometry are available in the modules to extract the required information. It is important to note, that the nomenclature for corrvreckan is laid out for pixel sensors due to its origins in development, but is not strictly limited to pixel-like objects. Corrvreckan reproduces the mapping to pixels and planes from the `eudaq::StdEventConverter`, where the user implements the conversion from raw data to `eudaq::StdEvents`.

The geometry information is essential to allow corrvreckan to conduct advanced reconstruction of the data.

2.2.3. Flexible Event Building

Figure 4 Examples for event building in corryvreckan [2]

To cover a large variety of use-cases, the event building procedure in corryvreckan is highly flexible and configurable. It can seamlessly combine data from detectors with different readout schemes such as trigger-based, frame-based, or data-driven devices. Some examples for possible event building strategies are shown in Figure 4. The figure also illustrates how multiple triggers or data arrival outside the event definition is handled. These and more event building strategies are explained in more detail in [2].

3. CORRYMONITOR

Since corryvreckan provides much of the desired functionality, the main task of this project is to integrate corryvreckan seamlessly into EUDAQ2. This means creating an EUDAQ2 module, which internally calls corryvreckan, but is initialised, configured, started, stopped, reset, and terminated the same way as any other module by receiving commands from the RunControl.

To make the monitoring tool attractive for users, it is beneficial to require minimal input from the user to start the monitoring to maximise user convenience. This includes automatically finding the new run files for the monitoring and passing them to corryvreckan on start-up without requiring the user to provide the file names. The details of this feature are given in the Milestone report for this task [3]. There also the working principle of the CorryMonitor is outlined. To summarise, corryvreckan is called internally after all files to monitor have been created by the DCs. They are found by the CorryMonitor by extracting the file name format and using the *inotify* library to scan for changes in the directory, like the creation of a file.

As corryvreckan allows for configuration updates via command line at the execution start time, the CorryMonitor is setup in such a way that it is still possible to pass these arguments to corryvreckan via a parameter in the EUDAQ2 configuration file.

Details on the commands and code changes required in the EUDAQ2 and corryvreckan frameworks can be found in the Milestone report.

Figure 5 shows the corryvreckan graphical user interface when using the CorryMonitor, after starting the run on the RunControl window. The screenshot in this example shows the hitmaps of two planes populated with random values from the example Producer provided by EUDAQ2.

Figure 5 Screenshot of running CorryMonitor with the example Producers provided by EUDAQ2

4. OPERATING THE CORRYMONITOR

This section briefly describes how to use the CorryMonitor module. Needless to say, it requires the user to use EUDAQ2 as DAQ control system, as well as a corryvreckan installation.

4.1. CORRYVRECKAN CONFIGURATION

For corryvreckan the user needs to prepare a geometry file, for which an example has already been shown in Figure 3. Additionally, a configuration file for corryvreckan needs to be prepared, where the load order of corryvreckan modules is specified. This configuration file is also responsible for defining a corryvreckan::Event. Furthermore, it allows the user to define the plots which will be displayed in the graphical user interface. An example is shown in Figure 6.

```
[Corryvreckan]
detectors_file = "corrygeo.geo"
detectors_file_updated = "corrygeo_updated.geo"
histogram_file = "corry_histo_file_example.root"

[Metronome]
triggers = 1
event_length = 100s

[EventLoaderEUDAQ2]
type = "Ex0Raw"
eudaq_loglevel=INFO
buffer_depth=5
inclusive=1

[OnlineMonitor]
dut_plots = [["EventLoaderEUDAQ2/%DUT%/hRawValuesMap", "colz"],["EventLoaderEUDAQ2/%DUT%/hPixelRawValues", "log"]]
hitmaps = [["EventLoaderEUDAQ2/%DUT%/hRawValuesMap", "colz"]]
```

Figure 6 Example for a corryvreckan configuration file

4.2. EUDAQ2 CONFIGURATION

To initialise the module, the path to the corryvreckan executable needs to be specified. It should also be noted that the monitor needs to run on the same machine as the RunControl, as the monitor module needs access to the EUDAQ2 configuration file in order to extract information for the DCs.

In the EUDAQ2 configuration file, DCs which are to be monitored need to be specified. To match with the EventLoaderEUDAQ2 modules in corryvreckan, there is a parameter which matches either based on the “type” keyword for the EventLoaderEUDAQ2, or alternatively via the individual plane names in the geometry file.

Examples for the Monitor sections in the EUDAQ2 initialisation and configuration files are shown in Figure 7.

<pre>[Monitor.my_mon] CORRY_PATH = /your/path/to/corry #executable</pre>	<pre>[Monitor.my_mon] CORRY_CONFIG_PATH=corryconfig.conf CORRY_OPTIONS=-v INFO DATACollectors_TO_MONITOR = my_dc0 CORRESPONDING_EVENTLOADER_TYPES = Ex0raw</pre>
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Figure 7 Examples of sections for CorryMonitor in EUDAQ2 initialisation file (left) and configuration file (right)

With this setup corryvreckan will automatically launch as soon as the run is started with the EUDAQ2 RunControl. Upon receiving a stop signal, corryvreckan will attempt to close gracefully, and be forced to quit if closing takes longer than a fixed amount of time.

5. TEST CASES

5.1. CALICE AHCAL

The CorryMonitor was tested with real data for the first time when CALICE AHCAL group from Institute of Physics, Prague, offered to provide their test beam data. The monitoring was tested in a lab-setting with these data, via a Producer which emulated data taking. Figure 8 shows the hitmaps of the 38 layers of the prototype, similarly as in Figure 2. The pixels in the hitmaps correspond to the 3×3 cm² scintillating plates with SiPM-on-tile readout [4].

Figure 8 CorryMonitor displaying hitmaps of 38 AHCAL layers

The Milestone report describes the lessons learnt from this test in detail.

5.2. DUAL-READOUT CALORIMETER TEST BEAM

The monitoring was first tested at a test beam at the dual-readout calorimeter campaign for the group's electromagnetic-shower-sized prototype at the SPS, CERN. As EUDAQ2 was not used as the main DAQ control system, the CorryMonitor was only used to monitor the SiPM data from the central region of the prototype, where the readout was more granular [5]. Here one pixel corresponds to one fibre. While there is no longitudinal segmentation to the prototype, it was still possible to make use of the "plane" functionality for the event. Mapping low and high gain readout of the SiPMs to different planes allowed the user to easily distinguish between these two channels.

The hitmaps were used extensively to align the prototype with the beam. A photograph of the CorryMonitor at the test beam is shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9 Use of the CorryMonitor during a test beam of the dual-readout calorimeter group

5.3. TELEPIX2 TEST BEAM

The latest version of the monitoring was tested during a TelePix2 test beam campaign at DESY. This test beam proved an excellent opportunity to put the monitoring to test during data taking.

The setup consisted of the newest generation ALPIDE beam telescope and the TelePix2 sensor. As EUDAQ2 was used as DAQ control system, the monitoring was tested in the intended setting for the first time.

A picture of the setup is shown in Figure 10. The use of the ALPIDE beam telescope allowed to exploit the corryvreckan functionality like tracking and correlations to the fullest.

Figure 10 Test beam setup of the TelePix2 test beam [6]

Using the latest development branch of the monitoring in the EUDAQ2 repository, the group was able to control the data acquisition and monitor the incoming data simultaneously with EUDAQ2. Screenshots of the RunControl window and the monitoring window are shown in Figure 11.

Figure 11 Screenshot of the EUDAQ2 RunControl and CorryMonitor windows (with hitmaps and tracking plots) during data taking [6]

During this campaign it was possible to not only prove the on-the-fly event building, but also its tracking capabilities, which are shown in Figure 11 and Figure 12.

Figure 12 Screenshot of the EUDAQ2 RunControl and CorryMonitor windows (with plane correlations) during data taking [6]

5.4. CONCLUSIONS FROM THE TESTS

Overall, these tests showed that the CorryMonitor works as intended. They were also excellent opportunities to improve the implementation. Especially the AHCAL data showed some unexpected problems which are described in the Milestone report.

Also, the TelePix2 test beam showcased excellently the envisioned use-case for the developed CorryMonitor. Any problems encountered were reported back and promptly fixed.

6. IMPROVEMENTS TO THE MONITOR BEYOND THE TASKS GOAL

Another feature implemented in this monitoring, going beyond the scope of the deliverable, is the ability to read files on different machines. As test beam setups are sometimes not very flexible, it is possible that the DCs run on a different machine than the monitor.

However, so far the functionality of the monitor relies on running the setup on the same machine as the data taking takes place, because corryvreckan needs to be able to read the files from the DCs. Being able to read files from anywhere in the network allows for far more flexibility for the test beam user. While many solutions exist to read files across machines, the software XRootD is a well-established “data access system” used by a variety of particle physics experiments [7]. It is therefore an excellent candidate to integrate into the monitoring system as some familiarity with it can be assumed for the user base.

At this stage of the monitoring the setup of XRootD servers needs to be done by user. In order to read remote files via XRootD (henceforth referred to as XRootD files) within the EUDAQ2 framework, a specialised XRootDFileReader and XRootDDeserializer need to be implemented, making use of the existing C++ API [8].

The corresponding files can be included in the EUDAQ2 build with the USER_XROOTD_BUILD command. Structurally they follow the blueprint given by the native EUDAQ2 FileReader and FileDeserializer. Thus, they show the same behaviour and are integrated into the EUDAQ2 framework seamlessly.

6.1. AUTOMATED DETECTION OF DATA

Unfortunately, the inotify library used to detect new files for local monitoring does not provide a way to do the same with XRootD files.

Instead the CorryMonitor needs to regularly request access to the file and marks a success if the server does not answer with an error. For any DCs monitored locally the inotify structure is still used.

6.2. PASSING FILES TO CORRYVRECKAN

When passing a file to the `corryvreckan::EventLoaderEUDAQ2` there needs to be a distinction between local and XRootD files as these require different FileReaders. To this end, a new option `xrootd_file` with default value *false* is introduced to the `EventLoaderEUDAQ2`. This allows the user to choose the correct option. In the `CorryMonitor`, this option is passed automatically to the corresponding `EventLoader`.

6.3. TESTING OF THE XROOTD FUNCTIONALITY

The XRootD functionality was tested in a lab setting during the development. According to the documentation, any XRootD servers started on a machine are completely separated from any other instances on the same computer. Therefore, a multi-machine setup was not required and the testing could be done on the same computer.

In the testing setup the data was written to a folder which was shared via an XRootD server. The reading of the example data with the `XRootDFileReader` was successful, which could be proven by trying to read the same data without starting the XRootD server beforehand, in which case the monitoring failed. The resulting plots are essentially the same as Figure 5 (hitmaps with random data) and are not repeated here.

So far there was no opportunity to test the XRootD functionality at a test beam.

7. PROMOTING THE MONITOR

There were several opportunities to promote this project and start building a user base.

Firstly, this work was naturally presented at the AIDAinnova 3rd Annual Meeting in the WP3 session. In the discussion after the talk, one group from Institut Pluridisciplinaire Hubert Curien, Strasbourg, expressed interest in testing the monitoring for their test beam of the CE65 sensor for the ALICE-ITS3 detector.

The presentation at the AIDAinnova meeting directly led to an invitation by Roman Poeschl to present the same work at the DRD6 collaboration meeting at CERN. In a plenary session, the `CorryMonitor` was presented to all participants. Again, one group came forward interested in testing the monitoring at their upcoming test beam of a crystal dual-readout calorimeter at DESY. As they are planning on using the information from the beam telescopes to extrapolate to the prototype, the tracking functionality of `corryvreckan` would be very useful for them.

Finally, this was presented at the 12th Beam Telescopes and Test Beam Workshop in Edinburgh. In the discussion after the talk some groups came forward to request more information about the monitoring, although none directly stated interest in using it at their test beams.

8. CONCLUSION

Together with the work outlined in the Milestone report the monitoring software is in a good state to be used by a large user base. The CorryMonitor has undergone several successful testing phases, except for the XRootD functionality, and has been promoted at several conferences, where some groups expressed interest in using it in their test beam campaigns.

At the time of writing the process to integrate all work into the EUDAQ2 and corryvreckan main repositories has started. Still, some final details need ironing out and eventual feedback by users needs to be addressed.

Overall, the goal of having a functioning, versatile online monitoring tool for EUDAQ2 is in the final steps of being achieved.

9. REFERENCES

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ANNEX: GLOSSARY

Acronym	Definition
DAQ	Data Acquisition
DC	DataCollector
DUT	Device-under-test
SiPM	Silicon Photomultiplier